

PROBLEMS OF DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS AND BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN

Davlatjonova Nodira Makhmudjon kizi

Assistant, Department of Pediatrics and Neonatology, Urgench State
Medical Institute (Uzbekistan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18627977>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2026

Accepted: 11th February 2026

Online: 12th February 2026

KEYWORDS

To determine the importance of clinical, laboratory, and anamnestic criteria in the differential diagnosis of obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma in children

ABSTRACT

In pediatric pulmonology, obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma have clinically similar symptoms, and their differentiation in the early stages is an important diagnostic problem. In both cases, bronchial obstruction, shortness of breath, wheezing, and cough are observed, which can lead to incorrect diagnosis and ineffective treatment. The similarity of clinical symptoms, especially in young children, complicates differential diagnosis. Therefore, a comparative study of the clinical and laboratory characteristics of these diseases is relevant.

Introduction

In pediatric pulmonology, obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma have clinically similar symptoms, and their differentiation in the early stages is an important diagnostic problem. In both cases, bronchial obstruction, shortness of breath, wheezing, and cough are observed, which can lead to incorrect diagnosis and ineffective treatment. The similarity of clinical symptoms, especially in young children, complicates differential diagnosis. Therefore, a comparative study of the clinical and laboratory characteristics of these diseases is relevant.

Purpose of the study

To determine the importance of clinical, laboratory, and anamnestic criteria in the differential diagnosis of obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma in children.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on the example of children with obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma treated in the pediatric department. The clinical symptoms of patients (cough characteristics, shortness of breath, duration of bronchial obstruction), the number of relapses of the disease, and their response to treatment were assessed. The history included allergic background, hereditary predisposition and environmental factors. Laboratory tests included a complete blood count, eosinophil level and inflammatory markers.

Results and discussion

According to the results of the analysis, obstructive bronchitis often develops against the background of acute respiratory infection, and bronchial obstruction is characterized by short-term and completely reversible. In bronchial asthma, recurrence of obstructive episodes, the presence of an allergic history and hypersensitivity to broncholytic agents are

determined. Laboratory tests showed a higher incidence of eosinophilia in children with asthma. These differences are important criteria for differential diagnosis.

Conclusions

Differential diagnosis of obstructive bronchitis and bronchial asthma in children requires a comprehensive approach. Joint assessment of clinical signs, anamnestic data and laboratory indicators is important for early and correct diagnosis, as well as for choosing optimal treatment tactics..

References:

- 1.Kalandarova, G. D., Raxmonova, S. A., Shamuratova, N. S., & Davlatjonova, N. M. (2023). THE LAWS OF CORRECT DIET AND THE CONSEQUENCES OF IMPROPER DIET. *Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing*, 1 (8), 64–67.
- 2.Davlatjonova, N. M., & Xudayberganov, M. R. (2024). OVQATLANISH BUZILISHI UCHUN XAVF OMILLARINING MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING JISMONIY O 'SISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI KO 'RSATKICHLARI BILAN O 'ZARO BOG 'LIQLIGI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 54), 127-130.
- 3.Makhmudovna, D. N. (2023). HYGIENIC CONTROL OF THE DIET OF RESIDENTS LIVING IN CONDITIONS OF RADIOACTIVE LOADS. *Confrencea*, 11(1), 2-6.
- 4.Бабаджанова, Ф., & Давлатжонова, Н. (2025). РОЛЬ БИОИМПЕДАНСОМЕТРИИ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ СОСТАВА ТЕЛА У ДЕТЕЙ С ВРОЖДЁННЫМИ ПОРОКАМИ СЕРДЦА. *SOUTH ARAL SEA MEDICAL JOURNAL*, 1(3), 243-253.
- 5.Шарипова, С. М., & Кобулов, Б. М. (2024). РОЛЬ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ ДЕТЕЙ ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 60), 200-202.
- 6.Атажанов, Х. П., & Оллаберганова, Ш. М. (2025). Dynamics of Spirometric Level in Patients with Cystic Fibrosis in the Aral Sea Region. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 49, 30-32.
- 7.Atajanov, K. P., Ollaberganova, S. M., & Masharipova, R. T. (2025, December). CHARACTERISTICS OF IRON METABOLISM IN RURAL PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH MILD IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA. In *International Conference on Health & Technology* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 26-28).
- 8.Atajanov, K. P., & Ollaberganova, S. M. (2025, December). ECHOGRAPHIC DIAGNOSIS OF PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN. In *International Conference on Medicine & Agriculture* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 18-20).